

European Clinical Research Alliance on Infectious Diseases (ECRAID)-Base Master Data Management Plan

Version 0

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the data management-related tools, processes and procedures for ECRAID-Base (<https://www.ecraid.eu/projects/ecraid-base/about-ecraid-base>). The DMP was developed first, based on the ECRAID-Base proposal and subsequently updated as the perpetual observational studies (POSS) have come online and the specifications obtained during the information gathering and analysis process. The DMP will be used for all data management related activities for all POSS within ECRAID-Base other than the REMAP-CAP study, described in detail elsewhere.

The DMP is designed to ensure optimal collection, processing, storage, and dissemination of the project's data, including making it as compliant as possible with FAIR principles, by - for example - proposing secure methodologies for data collection and storage, promoting interoperability through the adoption of data and metadata standards, and facilitating data sharing.

The DMP describes the overarching elements of the data management policy that will be used by beneficiaries for all the datasets that will be generated by the project. Implementation details that only apply to specific tasks, work packages or studies will be documented separately (e.g., specifications of eCRFs, lab procedures, or reports; procedures for data mapping, or dataset delivery; and policies for database validation and monitoring).

This version of the DMP reflects the current knowledge of the data management requirements for ECRAID-Base as of 02 June 2023. At this stage, only POS-VAP and POS-cUTI studies are live and actively enrolling participants. The DMP is a living document and will be updated at least yearly as POSs are launched.

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Researchers

Priya Shreedhar (orcid:0000-0002-1920-2636), Lauren Maxwell (orcid:0000-0002-0777-2092), Ankur Krishnan (orcid:0000-0001-8671-7421), Frank Leus (orcid:0000-0003-3469-914X), Steve Canham (orcid:0000-0002-4409-8834)

Organizations

Heidelberg University Hospital, European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN), University Medical Center Utrecht

Datasets

Title: [Perpetual Observational Study on Ventilator-associated Pneumonia](#)

Template: [Horizon 2020](#)

Background and Rationale: Ventilator Associated Pneumonia (VAP) is one of the most frequent healthcare associated infections in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) and a significant burden among ICU patients under Invasive Mechanical Ventilation (IMV). Several preventive and therapeutic treatment options are being developed in the field of VAP that will require evaluation in future randomized controlled trials (RCTs).

RCTs are the gold standard for evaluating medical interventions but are difficult to perform in a population at risk of, or with, VAP. These trials are challenging since it is difficult to recruit a large enough volume of high-quality centers to achieve the required number of recruited patients, especially if the focus is on specific patient groups (e.g., VAP due to a specific pathogen), for which site selection can be even more challenging and time consuming. There is a need for a well-organized and well-trained international network of ICUs focusing on VAP research that enables efficient execution of RCTs on preventive and curative interventions in this population. Through a Perpetual Observational Study (POS) we can provide quick access to a network of sites that fulfill pre-specified criteria. Additionally, the structured network of POS sites within ECRAID will maintain a continuous activity to carry out observational studies in this specific field, implementing informed consent, increasing quality and efficiency, and facilitating contracting.

Objectives: Overarching objective: To build a sustainable European clinical research network of ICUs that serves as a platform to facilitate observational and randomized VAP research activities

- Primary objectives: To implement through the POS, novel observational studies and RCTs aimed at improving VAP understanding, prevention, diagnosis and treatment. To have at least 30% of sites active in POS-VAP actively recruiting for an embedded observational study or RCT. To have at least 25% of all POS-VAP enrolled patients, enrolled within embedded observational studies or RCTs.
- Secondary objective: To continuously evaluate VAP clinical and microbiological epidemiology in European ICUs.
- Exploratory objectives: To determine the overall quality of patient enrolment, follow-up, and data collection.

Study design: Prospective perpetual observational study (POS).

Observational studies and RCTs can be embedded, simultaneously or sequentially, within the same site (if there is no interaction), or in separate sites.

Study population: All patients admitted to an ICU expected to remain under invasive mechanical ventilation for at least 48 hours are eligible to participate in the study.

20 000 patients are expected to be enrolled during the current funding period.

Countries and number of sites: 40 ICU sites in 15 European countries

Dataset Description

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- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

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- gene sequencing data)

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- Text files
- Numerical
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- Instrument specific formats

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?

Primary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

GB (gigabyte)

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Economy
- The public
- Industry

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)

In addition to DCAT, we also plan to use: DDI, CEDAR Template Model and Protocol Data Element Definitions

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

NCI Thesaurus

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Please provide more details and examples on used naming conversions

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Number_Date

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Yes

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

ECRAID data will be shared through an infrastructure that assigns a PID to the dataset.

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

3.1.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Metadata repository

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Yes

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Yes

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

Yes

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

Yes

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?

No

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

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- Repository of Archive

EMBL-EBI

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secure with backup and recovery

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

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Data can be accessed through a Trusted/Digital Research Environment (anDREa)

3.1.2.9 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

no auxiliary data

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

Yes

We use CDISC CT, MedDRA, ATC/DDD codes, SNOMED and LOINC

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

immediately

3.1.4.4 What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

CC-BY-SA

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

Yes

3.1.4.7 Describe the data quality assurance processes

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

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Frank Leus (orcid:0000-0003-3469-914X)

Data Management Lead

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- Other
- Personal Archive

Project/consortium specific archive

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Yes

6.1.2 Are the described data sensitive?

Yes

6.1.3 Are the described data personal?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing sensitive/personal data?

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- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies
- National laws

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

Title: Perpetual Observational Study on complicated Urinary Tract Infections

Template: Horizon 2020

Objectives:

Strategical:

- To provide an infrastructure capable of rapidly implementing randomised controlled trials (RCT) and other clinical trials related to cUTI.
- To continuously evaluate best practices related to patient enrolment and data collection to improve study execution.
- To collect information to support the design of innovative clinical trials and population enrichment.
- To align local practices in diagnosing and treating cUTI in the study sites.

Scientific:

Primary objective: To delineate the outcomes of patients with cUTI, and the impact of management-related variables; specifically:

- To determine the incidence of treatment failure in patients with cUTI.
- To determine modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors for treatment failure in patients with cUTI.

Secondary objectives:

- To describe the patient population with cUTI and the microbiological aetiology of cUTI in the study sites.
- To determine the rate of recurrences and superinfections, and those caused by multidrug-resistant organisms.
- To determine the mortality and its predictors in patients with cUTI.
- To determine the length of hospital stay after cUTI.

- To investigate outcomes (treatment failure and mortality) and outcome predictors in subgroup of patients, including elderly patients, patients with urinary catheter, bacteraemic and bacteraemia, ICU patients, patients with nosocomial cUTI, patients with multidrug-resistant pathogens.
- To describe variations in current practices in treating cUTI in the study sites.

Study design: Prospective perpetual observational study (POS).

Observational studies and RCTs can be embedded, simultaneously or sequentially, within the same site (if there is no interaction), or in separate sites.

Study population: Patients admitted to the participating hospitals with cUTI or developing cUTI during hospital stay.

17 000 patients are expected to be enrolled during the current funding period.

Countries and number of sites: Appr. 40 ICU sites in appr. 15 European countries. The expected enrolment is 100 patients per site per year.

Dataset Description

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- data from surveys)
- experimental (e.g.
- gene sequencing data)

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

- Text files
- Numerical
- Discipline specific formats
- Instrument specific formats
- Specimen collections

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?

Primary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

GB (gigabyte)

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Economy
- The public
- Industry

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

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3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)

In addition to DCAT, we also plan to use: DDI, CEDAR Template Model and Protocol Data Element Definitions

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

NCI Thesaurus

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Please provide more details and examples on used naming conversions

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3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

ECRAID data will be shared through an infrastructure that assigns a PID to the dataset.

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

3.1.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Metadata repository

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Yes

Extensible Markup Language

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

Yes

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

Yes

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?

No

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

- Project website
- Domain-specific database
- Repository of Archive

EMBL-EBI

3.1.2.5 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

secure with backup and recovery

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

Yes

3.1.2.7 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the data

Data can be accessed through a Trusted/Digital Research Environment (anDREa)

3.1.2.9 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

no auxiliary data

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

Yes

We use CDISC CT, MedDRA, ATC/DDD codes, SNOMED and LOINC

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

immediately

3.1.4.4 What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

CC-BY-SA

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

Yes

3.1.4.7 Describe the data quality assurance processes

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

3.1.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

Less than 2 years

4.1 Allocation of resources

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4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

- Other
- Personal Archive

Project/consortium specific archive

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

Yes

6.1.2 Are the described data sensitive?

Yes

6.1.3 Are the described data personal?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing sensitive/personal data?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies
- National laws

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

Title: Perpetual Observational Study on Acute Respiratory Infections in Emergency Rooms

Template: Horizon 2020

Objectives:

Primary:

- To describe variations in routinely used diagnostic approaches and clinical management in adult patients.
- To describe clinical outcomes in adults with community acquired ARI in acute hospital settings in Europe.

Secondary:

- To characterise the adult patient population with ARI presenting to acute hospital settings in Europe.
- To describe the aetiology of ARI in adults presenting to acute hospital settings in Europe.

Exploratory:

To assess the association between clinical outcomes and diagnostic or treatment related variables, for different aetiologies of community acquired ARI in adults presenting to hospital across Europe

Study design: The POS-ARI/ER study is a perpetual, observational study, which will assess clinical outcomes for different aetiologies of community acquired ARI and provide data to clinically characterise ARI in adults presenting to hospital settings across Europe, as well as serve as an overarching platform for delivery of embedded randomised controlled trials (RCTs) and other clinical studies related to diagnosis and treatment of ARI.

The Core POS-ARI/ER study will perpetually enrol a prospectively defined and sufficiently sized patient cohort that will allow investigations of relative contributions of diagnostic and therapeutic practices in the outcomes of mild, moderate and severe ARI of different aetiologies. Following a randomisation

process, subset of participants will have a single upper respiratory tract research sample (e.g. nose/throat swab) obtained at enrolment (within 24 hours), which will be sent to UA for pathogen detection by molecular methods (multiplex assay); these will be stored appropriately and analysed retrospectively. Standardised data collection forms will be used to capture baseline data on patient demographics, symptomatology, and the results and methods of clinical investigations as conducted as part of routine care. Patients will be followed until day 28 after enrolment to capture data on further relevant clinical investigations conducted and their results, as well as clinical management, in-hospital complications and outcomes. CRFs will be designed to collect only essential data, available as part of routine clinical care records, to minimise burden on research staff performing data collection. Study samples will be transferred and analyzed in the central laboratory.

Study population: Adults (≥ 18 years old) presenting to acute hospital services with suspected community-acquired acute respiratory tract infection

Countries and number of sites: Approximately 40 hospital sites in approximately 10-12 European countries. The expected enrolment is 11,750 patients over the course of the study..

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Primary data

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EMBL-EBI

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7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

Title: [Perpetual Observational Study on Acute Respiratory Infections in Primary Care](#)

Template: [Horizon 2020](#)

POS-ARI-PC has two components:

Component 1:

To conduct a prospective, anonymous, multi-country, prospective audit-type registration to describe the presentation and management of patients presenting in primary care with ARI (POS-ARI-PC Audit).

Component 2 with 3 objectives:

To conduct a prospective, observational study of ARI patients in primary care to undergo study-specific sampling upon inclusion, and be followed up for 28 days to capture the aetiology of their ARI and describe clinical outcomes (POS-ARI-PC-Core).

Qualitative research methods study with clinicians, research professionals and patients (where indicated) to gain a deep understanding of the research process, meaning of results and to identify barriers and opportunities for implementation of relevant findings.

To use the infrastructure developed in the POS-ARI-PC including: eligibility criteria, key case report forms and capability in the research platform to achieve readiness for adding in studies that cover additional observational research questions ('embedded' observational studies), and for efficient, rapid pivoting into randomising ARI participants to answer questions about effectiveness of diagnostic, behavioural or therapeutic management strategies for ARI in primary care.

Study design: Component 1 will be delivered through a prospective, multi-country, anonymous, audit-type registration of presentation and management of approximately 2,000 patients presenting in PC annually.

Component 2 will be achieved by including approximately 400 ARI patients annually in a prospective observational study in primary care annually who will consent to undergo study-specific sampling upon inclusion, and followed up for 28 days for clinical outcomes.

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3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

3.1.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

Metadata repository

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.14 Please provide URL/Name for the used searchable metadata

a. <https://ecrin.org/clinical-research-metadata-repository>

ECRIN Clinical Research Metadata Repository

b. <https://fairsharing.org/search?fairsharingRegistry=Database>

FAIRsharing.org

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

Yes

Extensible Markup Language

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

Yes

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

Yes

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

Yes

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?

No

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

- Project website
- Domain-specific database
- Repository of Archive

EMBL-EBI

3.1.2.5 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

secure with backup and recovery

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

Yes

3.1.2.7 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the data

Data can be accessed through a Trusted/Digital Research Environment (anDREa)

3.1.2.9 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

no auxiliary data

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

Yes

We use CDISC CT, MedDRA, ATC/DDD codes, SNOMED and LOINC

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

immediately

3.1.4.4 What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

CC-BY-SA

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

Yes

3.1.4.7 Describe the data quality assurance processes

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

3.1.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

Less than 2 years

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure
- Collaboration with other Projects

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

Frank Leus (orcid:0000-0003-3469-914X)

Data Management Lead

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

- Other
- Personal Archive

Project/consortium specific archive

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

Yes

6.1.2 Are the described data sensitive?

Yes

6.1.3 Are the described data personal?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing sensitive/personal data?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies
- National laws

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

Title: [Perpetual Observational Study on Disease X \(unexplained febrile illness\)](#)

Template: [Horizon 2020](#)

Objectives:

Primary:

- To prospectively study and describe the aetiology, clinical management and clinical impact of atypical viral infections in immunocompromised patients in Europe
- To assess the utility of metagenomics as a tool to support clinical decision making
- To improve laboratory diagnosis of – and preparedness for emerging viral infections

Secondary:

- To develop a clinical research network for responding to any emerging pathogen
- To study intra-host viral evolution in the immunocompromised host

Study design: This is a Perpetual Observational Study (POS) in specialised infectious disease hospitals across Europe on severe unexplained febrile illness with unusual epidemiology and/or clinical presentation and of likely viral aetiology (Disease X). This POS serves as a warm-based study that - while addressing specific questions for the current study population - also can be pivoted to include patients in case of an unexpected disease outbreak for which clinical research is needed. This protocol has been designed to optimize prospective and systematic collection of data and biological samples in a format that can be easily aggregated, tabulated and analysed across different participating centres. It is based on the generic clinical research protocol developed and used in the UK for a protocolized way of follow-up of any rare infectious disease, such as cases of MERS, monkeypox, Ebola etc.

Patients or legal representatives will be asked consent and enrolled in the POS at the moment they are admitted to the hospital. At the time of enrolment demographic and clinical data will be collected, as well as data on immune status, and exposures including animal contact and travel history. Embedded in the processes of standard care, a minimally invasive generic clinical sampling protocol will be followed. Study subjects will be followed-up from admission and at least until the first outpatient follow-up visit after discharge. For a select group of patients with proven persistent viral infections the follow-up may be extended with the objective to describe the immune response and study within patient viral evolution - where relevant. Patients enrolled will not be subjected to study specific interventions and all data collected will be derived from standard care practices.

The POS-Disease X will initially be used to study the microbiological aetiology and outcomes of severe unexplained viral syndromes in immunocompromised patients, as well as variations in current local practices in diagnosis and treatment. Consequently, we will - collectively - investigate where (and how) alignment of practices across the participating sites can be achieved. This will be prioritized towards alignment of diagnostic procedures.

In later phases of the study, this protocol will serve as a framework to study (re)emerging viral diseases in outbreak settings. For this reason, the protocol is designed with some flexibility to ensure that it can accommodate different demands.

The ultimate ambition of the POS-Disease X is a cadre of trained clinical research specialists that can help roll-out Disease X protocols across ECRAID, based on tested protocols and methods evaluated and adapted through the POS. This includes contribution to the baseline biobank, and validated protocols for syndromic and catch-all diagnostic methods for evaluation of incoming patients, in collaboration with WP8 (LAB).

Study population: Adult patients (≥ 18 years) with unexplained infectious illness or suspected or confirmed infection with an (emerging) viral pathogen

Number of inclusions and sites: A total of 1600 patients will be included over the course of 3 years in 5-8 participating centres.

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- sample or specimen data
- observational (e.g.
- sensor data
- data from surveys)
- experimental (e.g.
- gene sequencing data)

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

- Text files
- Numerical
- Discipline specific formats
- Instrument specific formats
- Specimen collections

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?

Primary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

GB (gigabyte)

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Economy
- The public
- Industry

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

Yes

DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)

In addition to DCAT, we also plan to use: DDI, CEDAR Template Model and Protocol Data Element Definitions

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

NCI Thesaurus

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Please provide more details and examples on used naming conversions

ECRAID-Base_[Abbreviation for POS]_[Type of Document]_Version
Number_Date

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

ECRAID data will be shared through an infrastructure that assigns a PID to the dataset.

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

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